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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	Enhanced Lipidomics Workflows for Plasma and Extracellular Vesicles through Advanced Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry Integrated		
Document creation date	12/16/2024	Corresponding Email	migueelpatricio@usp.br
Principal investigator	Miguel Rocha Patricio, GEBIL	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Universidade de São Paulo - USP Ribeirão Preto	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	None	Special conditions	Describe in the paper
2-phase system	Bligh and Dyer, MTBE and Hibrid	Derivatization	-

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate, Ammonium formate, Acetic acid	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS1	40000
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS1	1
Separation type 1	LC	Recording mode of raw data at MS1	Centroid mode
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
MS type	TOF	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	40000
MS vendor	SCIEX	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	1
Ion source	APCI	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
MS Level	MS1, MS2	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	High resolution		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Internal standard blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	Yes
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	No	Guidelines followed	FDA
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Raw data upload	Available on request
Are metadata available?	Available on request	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Breast Cancer Samples / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Additives	None
Provided preanalytical information	-	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) CAR[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CAR	Which assumptions were presumed?	Retention time, intensity and fragmentation pattern.
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name	[C4H5O2 ⁺] 85.02 m/z		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

1) CAR[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

2) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
(m/z 184.072, 1000, C ₅ H ₁₅ NO ₄ P ⁺)			
(m/z 264.258, 10, C ₁₈ H ₃₄ N ⁺)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

2) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

3) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
-FA2(+H)			
HG(PC,184)			
-H2O			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

3) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

4) TG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
FA1			
FA2			
FA3			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

4) TG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

5) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
HG(PC,184)			
(C5H13NO,104)-(H2O)			
-H2O			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

5) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

6) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
HG			
-FA1(+H)			
-H2O			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

6) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

7) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
HG			
-FA1(+H)			
-H2O			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

7) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

8) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
-(H2O,18)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

8) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

9) PI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
-HG(PI,260+H)			
-FA2(+H) - (PI,260+H)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

9) PI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

10) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
	Fragment name		
	-HG(PS,185)		
	FA1		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

10) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

11) PC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
	Fragment name		
	HG(PC,184)		
	FA		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

11) PC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

12) PE O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE O	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
-HG(PE,141)			
FA			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

12) PE O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

13) FA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
HG			
Neutral Loss			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

13) FA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

14) Cer[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
FA			
HG			
-(-H)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

14) Cer[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

15) Hex2Cer[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
-(-H)			
FA1(+C2H3NO)			
-HG(Hex2,324)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

15) Hex2Cer[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

16) ST[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	ST	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
	Fragment name		
	HG		
	FA		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

16) ST[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

17) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPI	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
	Fragment name		
	HG(PI,241)		
	FA1(+O)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

17) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-